

J.K. ROWLING'S HARRY POTTER NOVELS' STYLISTIC ELEMENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12525981>

Annotation

The article deals with the stylistic features of the Harry Potter series of novels by the British writer J.K. Rowling. The article examines some stylistic devices and expressional means characteristic of literature of this genre and determines their role in these works. In this very work mainly the descriptive method was used.

Keywords Literary work, stylistic features, stylistic device, expressional means.

Аннотация

Статья посвящена стилистическим особенностям серии романов «Гарри Поттер» британской писательницы Джоан К. Роулинг. Целью исследования было рассмотреть некоторые стилистические приемы и выразительные средства, характерные для литературы такого жанра. Задачей являлось выделение таковых и определение их роли в исследуемом произведении. В данной работе главным образом был использован описательный исследования.

Ключевые слова Литературное произведение, стилистические особенности, стилистический прием, выразительные средства.

Let's imagine for a while that our speech would not contain figurative characteristics and linguistic units that carry additional meaning and reflect our attitude towards the spoken statement and the person to whom our speech is directed. Most likely, it would not be like communication between living people, but would resemble a conversation of some robots or machines that use words that do not contain any emotional connotation. Expressiveness and the beauty of speech is important not only in the process of oral statements in everyday life communication, but these features play a very important role in fiction.

Indeed, it is difficult for us to imagine any prosaic or poetic a work that would not contain expressive means or stylistic techniques.

Consideration of the linguistic features of elements of fiction happened and continues to happen, dividing stylistic means into visual and expressive means. Means called expressive do not create images, but enhance

expressiveness of speech, while enhancing its emotionality with the help of special syntactic constructions such as inversion, rhetorical question, parallel designs, etc. Visual means, being mainly lexical, serve for description. This group includes the following types of figurative use of words: and expressions such as epithet, metaphor, metonymy, litotes, hyperbole, irony, etc. They used by authors of works to convey all types of figurative use words, phrases and phonemes.

JK Rowling is the author of a series of novels about the adventures of a boy named Harry Potter, who suddenly finds out that he is a wizard. For seven books, the reader follows the fate of a boy at Hogwarts School of Witchcraft and Wizardry. The use of stylistic devices and means of expression in the works of Joan K. Rowling can be traced through the example of one of the characters in the book - a potions professor Severus Snape, since this character leaves two impressions from his first appearance the aftertaste and its role remain unclear to the reader until the last book in the series novels. Characteristic of it is: a) irony - a technique through which there is an interaction between two types of lexical meanings based on the relationship opposites: "Yes, it is easy to see that nearly six years of magical education have not been wasted on you, Potter. Ghosts are transparent." [3]; "...is the imprint of a departed soul left upon the earth...and of course, as Potter so wisely tells us, transparent." [3]; "...the train isn't good enough for the famous Harry Potter and his faithful sidekick Weasley" [3]; b) hyperbole, which is a technique of exaggeration and from the point of view of real possibilities of implementation seem doubtful: "A five - year old could have told us as much," sneered Snape" [3]; c) pun - a play on words generated by homonymy or similarity of sound and causing a comic effect: "I would expect nothing more sophisticated from you, Ronald Weasley, the boy so solid he cannot Apparate half an inch across a room" [3].

A striking stylistic device used by JK Rowling is application of inversion. The author uses it to strengthen the attitude of the characters to this or that another event, for example, Harry's negative attitude towards potions lessons: "Worst of all were Professor Snape's classes down in the dungeons, where their breath rose in a mist before them and they kept as close as possible to their hot cauldrons" [3]. It is worth noting that For each individual character, the author has selected individual stylistic techniques that accurately characterize some, but are not suitable for others characters. So for the gamekeeper Hagrid, the technique of intentional spelling errors to reflect his Somerset accent: "Las' time,

you were ,Yeh, yer, yeh've got, fer cryin'." [3 - 5] This technique is not applicable for Severus Snape, who was a descendant of the "pure blood" dynasty.

A good literary work must leave a mark on the mind reader. And this trace can be both positive and negative. Both in the first and In the second case, the impression the reader receives requires further reflection. The work we are considering is one of these. The charm of the Harry Potter novels comes from proper use. stylistic devices that vividly express characters, places and events. The author's task was to make the reader plunge into the magical world, feel the emotions of the characters novel, understand their actions, using all kinds of stylistic devices. And in this she succeeded brilliantly.

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